

SHORT COMMUNICATION

N-Methyl Salicyl Hydroxamic Acid and its Metal Chelates

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The chelating properties of N-phenyl salicyl hydroxamic acid are being studied in this laboratory and some publications¹ have been made. In order to study the effect of substitution of methyl group in place of phenyl group in the ligand already mentioned, N-methyl salicyl hydroxamic acid (RH₂) has been prepared by condensing salicyl chloride with N-methyl hydroxylamine.

The compound melts at 136° [Found : N, 8.26; C₈H₉O₃ N, requires 8.38%].

By controlling pH, the following metal chelates have been prepared :

Cu(RH)₂, Cd(RH)₂, Ni(RH)₂, Fe(RH)₃, Al(RH)₃, VO(OH)(RH)₂ and UO₂(RH)₂. It has been observed that in the cases of Fe(III) and U(VI) intense coloration takes place at lower pH before precipitation at higher pH. The measurement of magnetic susceptibility of some of the chelates indicates that they are high spin complexes.

Quantitative precipitation of Cu(RH)₂ takes place at pH = 4.5–5.0, but there is no precipitation of Cd(II) chelate. So the gravimetric estimation of Cu(II) in presence of Cd(II) has been made possible using N-methyl salicyl hydroxamic acid as the precipitating agent at pH = 4.5 to 5.0 and weighing the precipitate as Cu(RH)₂ after drying at 110°. The pH has been controlled with acetic acid—sodium acetate (2 : 3) buffer (pH = 5.0). From the filtrate Cd(II) has been estimated by precipitating as CdS and then iodimetrically. Thus it is apparent that Cd(II) may be detected by classical methods in the supernatant liquid on centrifuging the precipitate Cu(RH)₂. Further studies are in progress.

Details will be communicated in due course.

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1. N. N. Ghosh and Aruna Bhattacharyya, *This Journal*, 1964, **41**, 311; 1967, **44**, 972; 1968, **45**, (accepted for publication).

